

IN INVESTMENT AUTHORITY AND ECONOMY INNOVATIVE WAYS TO USE IT EFFICIENTLY

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Annotation. In this article, the scientific and theoretical views on the investment potential are presented, the method of effective use of investments is highlighted, indicators of investment in the economy of our country are analyzed, and suggestions are given on the effective use of investment potential.

Keywords: investments, investment potential, factors influencing investment volume, multiplier effect, investment sources, domestic investments, innovative ways of effective use of investment potential.

Introduction. In the next stages of the economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan, a lot of attention is being paid to the issues of increasing the country's investment potential and increasing the volume of investments in the economy. In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the task "to further improve the investment environment in the country and increase its attractiveness, to take measures to attract 120 billion US dollars, including 70 billion dollars of foreign investments in the next five years" [1].

In his speech at the Tashkent International Investment Forum, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke about the results achieved in recent years in terms of investment in the country's economic reform, including the annual volume of foreign investments attracted to our economy in the last 5 years, which increased by three and a half times, and their total value was 25 billion dollars. Due to this, over 2.5 million new jobs were created as a result of the implementation of 59,000 investment projects [2].

It is expected that 14 billion US dollars worth of investment will be attracted to Uzbekistan in the next five years on the basis of public-private partnership in

energy, transport, healthcare, education, ecology, communal services, water management and other sectors. It is envisaged to establish foreign economic relations between the republic's territories and business representatives of foreign countries [1].

The future development of new Uzbekistan is directly related to investment in the economy, and in this regard, effective use of the existing investment potential is of great importance. Therefore, the topic of this work is relevant today.

The purpose of this study is to illuminate scientific concepts related to investment potential and to propose measures for effective use of the country's investment potential.

The tasks of the research are to clarify the theoretical concepts related to investment potential, to analyze the indicators of investment in the country's economy, to methodically justify the processes of effective use of investments, and to develop measures for the effective use of existing investment potential.

The results of this research are based on the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" No. to a certain extent, it helps to ensure the implementation of Decree No. PF-5717 and No. PF-6042 dated August 18, 2020 "On additional measures for further development of export and investment potential in the Republic".

Analysis of literature on the topic

Many foreign and local economists have expressed their opinions about the investment potential of the country and its regions. Including:

Romanian scientists have justified the fact that foreign companies entering the country's national economy take regional characteristics into account in their investment strategies. According to their research, investors see Romanian regions as 2 separate economic regions. The availability of new markets, skilled workforce and infrastructure opportunities are cited as important factors in attracting

investments in the first region. The second region attracted investors due to its low prices [3].

Chinese scientist F. Xiaolan analyzes the impact of the increase in the country's innovation potential on productivity. According to his research, investment has a significant positive effect on overall innovation capacity. But this effect will depend on the absorptive capacity of the receiving national economy and the availability of innovation-providing factors [4].

According to Arab scientists Ch. Emirullah and M. Azam, "Investment potential is directly related to macroeconomic stability, political stability, development of local capital markets, management environment, legislative framework, efficiency of state bodies, level of corruption and market conditions" [5].

A. M. Margolin, one of the Russian scientists, states that "Investment potential is a set of investment resources arranged to a certain extent, and their use ensures achieving the effect of synergism" [6].

According to S.A. Trukhin, "Investment potential is determined by evaluating labor, consumption, production, financial, institutional, innovative, infrastructure and natural resource potential" [7].

expresses the view that "Economic-geographic conditions, saturation with production factors, living standards of the population, their consumption demand determine the investment potential of the region" [8].

According to L. D. Zubkova, "He understands the need for investments (investment demand and supply) as a set of objective features, tools, opportunities, factors (availability of investment resources and directions for their use)"[9].

E. In his research, Abramov recommends the use of indicators including the level of development of the economy and infrastructures, the provision of financial resources, the demographic situation, the development of market relations, and the

level of security of investment activity when calculating the level of investment attractiveness of regions [10].

According to Sh. Mustafakulov, one of the economists from Uzbekistan, the investment potential of regions should be divided into 9 groups of factors (natural resource potential, production potential, innovative potential, labor potential, financial potential, institutional potential, infrastructure potential, consumer potential, tourist potential) possible [11].

Factors determining the investment potential were studied by the economist B. Valiev into 10 groups (production potential, investment activity, labor potential, consumption potential, natural resources potential, infrastructure potential, institutional, export, innovative, scientific and educational potential) and based on these factors, the investment potential of the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan was evaluated [12]. According to the results of this research, according to the level of investment potential, the regions of the Republic are divided into 3 groups (high, medium, low level).

In our opinion, the investment potential consists of the free funds of the state, population, enterprises and organizations, and the state should develop a system that encourages the processes of introducing these funds into the economy as investment and increase the volume of investments into the economy by implementing it.

Research methodology

When assessing the investment potential, it is necessary to pay attention to the factors affecting the volume of investments.

Two main factors determine the level of investment:

- 1) expected profit rate from investment costs;
- 2) interest rate.

Profit is the driving motive for investment costs. Entrepreneurs make investments only if they make a profit.

The second factor that determines the level of investment is the interest rate. The interest rate is the amount of money that must be paid on the loan capital obtained from the bank, which is necessary to purchase the principal capital.

Analysis and results

If we analyze the amount of investments that will be attracted to the economy of our country in the following years, in 2020, the total financing sources for the development of economic and social spheres in the Republic of Uzbekistan will amount to 202.0 trillion soums was absorbed. 20.1 billion in dollar equivalent. US dollars. was absorbed and made 91.8% compared to 2019.

A decrease in investment activity was observed in Uzbekistan in 2020, compared to 2019, the growth rate of investments in fixed capital was 91.8%. In 2020, 202.0 trillion soums of fixed capital investments were absorbed, of which 65.4% or 132.0 trillion soums. 34.6% or 70.0 trillion soums from the funds raised. soums were appropriated at the expense of enterprises and residents' own funds. 39,310.2 billion from centralized financing sources. soums or 19.5% of total investments and 8.0% less investments in fixed capital compared to 2019. 162,689.9 billion at the expense of decentralized financing sources. soums or 80.5% of the total volume of investments were absorbed, and this indicator increased by 8.0% compared to 2019. In 2020, enterprises and organizations will spend 51911.3 billion from their own funds. 25.7% of total investments were invested in fixed capital. 18,077.8 billion from population funds. soums or 8.9% were absorbed. 28,740.5 billion from direct foreign investments. soums were absorbed and decreased by 5.3 percentage points compared to 2019, making up 14.2% of total investments.

Capital investments in our country in 2021 will be 244.9 billion. amounted to soum. The share of fixed capital investment in GDP was equal to 33.3 percent, and the growth of fixed capital investment in 2021 was 105.2 percent by 2020 [14].

Trillion soums more investment was made in the economy of Uzbekistan in 2021 than in 2020, and we calculated its increase based on the multiplier effect using Table 1.

Table 1.

Increase of investments into the economy of Uzbekistan based on the multiplier effect [15] (trln. sum)

Changes in earnings	Changes in consumer spending	Change in savings
24	18	6
18	13.5	4.5
13.5	10,12	3.38
10,12	7.59	2.53
7.59	5.69	1.90
5.69	4.27	1.42
3.20	2.40	0.80
2.40	1.80	0.60
96	72	24

For this, the limited propensity to consume in our country is 0.75 and to save we assumed that the limited bias is 0.25. Therefore, investments in the economy will increase by 4 times based on the multiplier effect.

Conclusions and suggestions

As investment potential, it will be necessary to pay attention to the sources of investment. One of the sources of investments is the savings of the general population. It is one of the main sources of domestic investment.

When studying the sources of investment, it should be noted that in practice, the owner of the fund and the investor may or may not be the same person. Usually, savings are made by most entities in society, and their use as an investment can be made by completely different entities. Also, the fund of industrial, agricultural and

other enterprises operating in the economy is also a source of investment. In this case, "accumulator" and "investor" are embodied in one entity.

Investments are mainly made at the expense of the following sources: first, investors' own financial resources (profits, depreciation deductions, cash reserves, etc.);

secondly, borrowed financial resources (bonds, bank loans);

thirdly, financial resources involved (funds from the sale of shares, shares and other payments of individuals and legal entities);

fourth, state budget funds;

fifth, other funds.

The structure of investment financing sources in Uzbekistan is changing in recent years. In particular, the share of state budget funds is decreasing year by year, and the share of population funds, enterprise funds, foreign direct investment and non-budget funds is increasing.

On the basis of the above, it is necessary to further accelerate the measures to introduce free funds of enterprises and residents into the economy as internal investment, and implement various measures that will increase their interest in this regard.

In order to effectively use the investment potential in the process of economic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

first, further acceleration of measures to improve the investment infrastructure;

secondly, to sharply reduce the role and share of the state in the economy, including the effective sale of the state's share of shares of state-owned enterprises to potential investors;

thirdly, to focus on increasing the volume of investments in human capital in our country;

fourth, to further accelerate the processes of digitalization of the economy, to focus on "green" technologies and innovative approaches in making investments;

fifth, increasing the investment attractiveness of our country and its regions, further improving the business environment in them, etc.

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